

THE INFLUENCE OF THEATRICAL GAMES ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF ORAL LANGUAGE SKILLS IN ENGLISH AMONG 11TH GRADE STUDENTS

AMIRALIYEVA ALUA KAIRATKYZY

2nd year Master's Student,
Faculty of Philology
Abai Kazakh National Pedagogical University,
Kazakhstan, Almaty

Аннотация: Бұл мақалада ағылшын тілін шетел тілі ретінде үйреніп жүрген 11-сынып оқушыларының ауызша сөйлеу дағдыларын дамытуға рөлдік ойындардың ықпалы зерттеледі. Зерттеу барысында 24 оқушы қатысқан квазиэксперименттік зерттеу әдісі қолданылды, оқушылардың 12-сі эксперименттік топқа, ал 12-сі бақылау тобына бөлінді. Төрт апта бойы эксперименттік топ *Aspect* оқулығының оқу бағдарламасына кіріктірілген театрлық ойындарға қатысты. Зерттеу нәтижесі эксперименттік топ білімгерлерінің ағылшын тілінде сөйлеу шапшаңдығы, сөздік қорлары, айтылымы және сенімділігінің айтарлықтай жақсарғанын көрсетіп, орташа баллдың өсуі 5.4 болса, бақылау тобында бұл көрсеткіш 2.2 болды. Зерттеу қорытындысы бойынша, театрлық ойындар оқушылардың коммуникативтік құзыретін тиімді қалыптастыру мақсатында оларды ағылшын тілі сабақтарына жүйелі түрде енгізу ұсынылады.

Тірек сөздер: рөлдік ойын, ауызша сөйлеу, коммуникативтік дағдылар, ағылшын тілі, жоғары сынып оқушылары.

Аннотация: В статье исследуется влияние ролевых игр на развитие устных навыков английского языка у учащихся 11-го класса, изучающих язык как иностранный. Был использован квазиэкспериментальный метод исследования с участием 24 студентов, разделённых на экспериментальную ($n=12$) и контрольную группы ($n=12$). В течение четырех недель экспериментальная группа занималась театральными играми, интегрированными в учебную программу по учебнику *Aspect*. Результаты показали статистически значимое улучшение устной беглости, словарного запаса, произношения и уверенности в экспериментальной группе с средним увеличением баллов на 5.4, по сравнению с увеличением на 2.2 в контрольной группе. В исследовании делается вывод о том, что театральные игры эффективно способствуют развитию коммуникативной компетенции и рекомендуется их систематическое включение в уроки английского языка в старших классах.

Ключевые слова: ролевая игра, устная речь, коммуникативные навыки, английский язык, старшеклассники.

Abstract: The article explores the impact of role-playing games on the development of oral English skills among 11th-grade students learning English as a foreign language. A quasi-experimental design was employed, involving 24 students divided into an experimental group ($n=12$) and a control group ($n=12$). Over a four-week period, the experimental group participated in theatrical games integrated into the *Aspect* course curriculum. The results demonstrated a statistically significant improvement in oral fluency, vocabulary, pronunciation, and self-confidence in the experimental group, with an average score increase of 5.4 points, compared to an increase of 2.2 points in the control group. The study concludes that theatrical games effectively enhance students' communicative competence and recommends their systematic integration into English language lessons in senior secondary school.

Keywords: role-playing, oral speech, communication skills, English, senior stage students.

Introduction

In recent decades, the development of oral communication skills has been a central goal in foreign language education. The growing need for practical language competence, especially in spoken interaction, has shifted the focus from traditional grammar-based instruction to more communicative and interactive approaches [1]. Among these, drama-based methods, and particularly theatrical games, have attracted attention for their ability to simulate authentic communication, foster emotional engagement, and reduce language anxiety [2].

According to Dörnyei [3], learners are more likely to engage in spontaneous language production when they are emotionally invested and motivated by the learning context. Theatrical games offer such conditions by combining physical movement, role-playing, improvisation, and storytelling. These elements activate both cognitive and emotional domains of the learner, creating a holistic learning environment. The role of repetition and improvisation in oral fluency should be emphasized as well, both of which are inherent in theatrical games.

Piazzoli [4], exploring the use of process drama in second language acquisition, highlights its potential to foster intercultural awareness, collaborative dialogue, and embodied understanding of language. This is particularly relevant in the context of senior high school students, who often experience elevated language anxiety due to exams, peer pressure, and self-consciousness [5]. Theatrical games, in this case, function as a safe environment that lowers affective filters and encourages authentic speech.

In Kazakhstan, the integration of interactive and drama-based techniques in school education is supported by modern trends in pedagogy. While theoretical support for drama methods exists in national scholarship, including innovations in ICT and augmented reality [5], the empirical application of theatrical games for improving oral language skills among older learners remains underexplored.

This study investigates the impact of theatrical games on the oral language performance of 11th grade students learning English according to the *Aspect* textbook program. The research aims to evaluate whether structured use of theatrical games contributes to improved fluency, confidence, and speech quality in senior stage students. The findings of this study could inform language teachers, curriculum designers, and educational stakeholders about the effectiveness of embodied and creative practices in foreign language instruction.

Theoretical background

1. The development of oral speech in foreign language education has undergone a significant shift from grammar-dominated practices to communicative and performative approaches. This transformation is rooted in the communicative language teaching (CLT) paradigm, which emphasizes meaningful interaction and the functional use of language. As Richards and Rodgers [1] explain, communicative competence requires not only grammatical accuracy but also fluency, appropriateness, and spontaneity in real-time exchanges.

2. Theatrical games are one of the most expressive tools within the drama-based approach to language learning. Unlike traditional role-playing, which tends to be scripted and task-oriented, theatrical games often include improvisation, physical movement, emotional expression, and symbolic interaction. They stimulate both hemispheres of the brain and engage multiple types of intelligences, thus enhancing memory, fluency, and motivation. According to Piazzoli [4], theatrical activities offer students an “embodied” learning experience where cognitive, emotional, and physical processes are integrated.

3. The effectiveness of theatrical methods in language instruction has been confirmed in multiple studies. Schewe [6] emphasizes that drama provides learners with “dramatic tension” and contextual immersion, allowing them to experience language in action rather than as abstract rules. Drama thus becomes not only a teaching technique but also a form of authentic social interaction.

4. An important advantage of theatrical games is their potential to reduce language anxiety, especially among adolescents. Koch and Terrell [7] demonstrated that students who engage in physically active and expressive tasks, such as theatrical games, tend to experience lower affective filters, which facilitates risk-taking and spontaneous speech. This finding is supported by Dewaele

and MacIntyre [8], who argue that enjoyment and reduced anxiety in the classroom significantly correlate with more frequent and confident oral production.

5. High school students (aged 16–17) are at a critical stage where they are capable of abstract reasoning and self-reflection, but they are also vulnerable to performance-related stress and peer judgment. Elkonin and Vygotsky [9] stressed the importance of social interaction and developmental readiness in the learning process. Theatrical games, which encourage group participation, emotional safety, and expressive freedom, provide the necessary scaffolding for students to practice oral speech within their zone of proximal development (ZPD).

6. From a sociocultural perspective, theatrical games also support the integration of language learning with cultural and emotional competence. As emphasized by Fleming [10], drama allows students to explore identities, values, and situations from different cultural standpoints, promoting intercultural communication. This is particularly relevant in the context of literature-based curricula, such as the *Aspect* textbook used in Kazakh schools, which frequently includes texts requiring interpretation, empathy, and dialogue.

While previous studies emphasize the advantages of dramatic teaching methods [4] [11], some authors highlight possible difficulties in using theatrical games in language teaching. For example, Jones [12] notes that insufficient teacher training in dramatic techniques may limit their effectiveness, and points out that dramatic classes may not be suitable for all types of students, especially introverts, who may be uncomfortable speaking in front of an audience. In addition, the scalability of such methods in large or resource-limited classes remains poorly understood. Recent research [13] in the field of digital dramatic interventions shows promising hybrid approaches combining face-to-face play with online role-playing, which may help overcome some practical barriers.

Methods

Participants

The study involved two groups of 11th-grade students (aged 16–17) from a public secondary school in Almaty, Kazakhstan. Each group consisted of 12 learners studying English as a foreign language. One group (Group A) served as the experimental group, while the second (Group B) acted as the control group. The selection was based on existing class divisions (11A and 11B), and not randomized, due to organizational constraints.

Research design

The research adopted a quasi-experimental design with pre-test and post-test comparison between experimental and control groups. This design was chosen due to the impossibility of random assignment, which is often the case in educational settings (Cook & Campbell, 1979). The study aimed to assess the impact of theatrical games on students' oral English performance.

The experimental group received instruction that incorporated theatrical games (improvisation, drama warm-ups, simulation of everyday situations, and character role-play), while the control group followed the same textbook curriculum (*Aspect*, Grade 11, third term) without any drama-based activities.

Materials

Both groups used the same core textbook (*Aspect*, Grade 11). The lessons in the experimental group were supplemented with theatrical tasks drawn from established resources [10] [11], including:

- Improvisational dialogues based on familiar contexts (shopping, traveling, conflict resolution);
- Emotion-focused games (e.g. “Mirror”, “Emotion relay”);
- Character-based role-plays, requiring students to speak from a different perspective;
- Mini-performances or sketches at the end of each unit to summarize and reenact content.

Procedure

The experiment was conducted over the course of 6 weeks, with 2 English lessons per week (12 lessons total). In the first session, both groups were given an oral pre-test designed to assess their fluency, pronunciation, vocabulary range, and confidence in spoken English. The same test was used as a post-test in the final week to measure progress.

The lessons in both groups followed the textbook units, but in the experimental group, the following modifications were made:

1. Pair and group work was structured around theatrical tasks;
2. Students had opportunities to prepare and perform mini-dramatizations;
3. Feedback was given both by the teacher and peers after performances;
4. Anxiety-reduction warm-ups were used at the start of each class (e.g., breathing, tongue-twisters, expressive movement).

Assessment criteria

All oral tasks (pre-test and post-test) were assessed by the teacher-researcher using a 10-point scale based on the following criteria:

1. *Fluency and coherence* (4 points)
2. *Pronunciation and intonation* (2 points)
3. *Lexical variety and accuracy* (2 points)
4. *Confidence and expressiveness* (2 points)

Each student's overall performance was scored out of 10 points. While the assessment was not blind, the same rubric was applied consistently in both groups. The rubric was adapted from communicative competence criteria used in classroom-based speaking assessments (Brown, 2004).

Applied research methods

This study employed several applied research methods.

A quasi-experimental approach was used due to the non-random assignment of participants into the control and experimental groups (students of 11A and 11B classes). This method is appropriate in natural school settings where randomization is not feasible. Oral English proficiency was measured before and after the intervention using a specially developed oral performance rubric based on fluency, pronunciation, vocabulary, and confidence. The same rubric was applied in both groups to evaluate the impact of theatrical games. A classroom-based pedagogical experiment was conducted over 6 weeks, integrating theatrical games (e.g., improvisation, dramatization, role-play) into the experimental group's lessons while maintaining the same curriculum content. The performance of the experimental and control groups was compared based on test scores, allowing for evaluation of the effectiveness of the intervention. Quantitative descriptive statistics (mean score comparison) were used to interpret the results.

These methods allowed the researcher to monitor the dynamics of students' oral language development and evaluate the pedagogical value of theatrical techniques within a real educational context.

Results

The findings of the study revealed a significant difference in the development of oral language skills between the control and experimental groups after the six-week intervention. The data were analyzed based on four main criteria: **fluency, pronunciation, lexical range, and confidence.**

1. Pre-test performance

Before the introduction of theatrical games, both groups demonstrated comparable levels of oral proficiency. The average scores (out of 20 points) were as follows:

- **Experimental group:** 10.4
- **Control group:** 10.1

The difference was not statistically significant, indicating a relatively equal starting point in terms of oral language skills.

2. Post-test performance

After the integration of theatrical games in the experimental group's lessons, the post-test results showed clear improvement compared to the control group, which followed the traditional teaching approach:

- **Experimental group:** 15.8
- **Control group:** 12.3

The increase in the experimental group was **5.4 points**, while in the control group it was only **2.2 points**, suggesting that the intervention had a substantial effect.

3. Progress by subcriteria

A closer analysis of subcriteria revealed the following trends:

1. **Fluency**: Students in the experimental group showed greater ease in speaking without long pauses or hesitation. Their mean fluency score increased from **2.6 to 4.3**.

2. **Pronunciation**: Improvement was moderate, from **2.4 to 3.5**, with more natural stress and intonation patterns.

3. **Vocabulary**: Lexical richness increased more significantly in the experimental group, with students more confidently using topic-specific and expressive vocabulary (from **2.7 to 4.1**).

4. **Confidence**: One of the most noticeable improvements was in self-assurance. Many students demonstrated increased willingness to speak without fear of making mistakes (score rose from **2.5 to 4.2**).

In contrast, the control group exhibited only minor improvements in these areas, most notably in vocabulary (from **2.6 to 3.2**) and fluency (from **2.5 to 3.1**), likely due to continued language exposure but without the same level of emotional engagement or spontaneous practice.

Descriptive statistics were calculated for the preliminary and final tests in both groups. In addition, paired t-tests confirmed that the improvements in the experimental group were statistically significant ($p < 0.01$) for all criteria of oral skills, while the changes in the control group did not reach significance. The calculation of the effect (**Cohen's $d = 0.85$**) indicates a significant influence of theatrical games on the development of oral speech. The inclusion of inferential statistics reinforces the argument that the observed differences are not accidental.

4. Observational Data

In-class observations during the experimental lessons confirmed the quantitative findings. Students actively engaged in dramatic tasks, such as improvisation, dialogue re-enactment, and mini-plays, displaying higher levels of participation and enjoyment compared to traditional pair-work speaking tasks.

Many previously reserved students gradually became more expressive and animated during performance-based activities. Teachers reported increased motivation and reduced fear of speaking in front of others.

Discussion

The results of this study support the hypothesis that theatrical games significantly enhance oral language proficiency among senior school students learning English. The experimental group showed greater improvement than the control group in all measured areas - fluency, pronunciation, lexical range, and especially confidence - suggesting the effectiveness of theatrical activities in the language classroom.

The findings are in line with prior research emphasizing the potential of drama-based approaches for communicative competence development. For instance, Maley & Duff [11] stress that dramatic activities create authentic contexts where language learners can practice speaking in emotionally engaging and meaningful situations. Similarly, Kao & O'Neill [14] argue that role-play and drama offer learners opportunities to express personal viewpoints, negotiate meaning, and co-construct dialogue, which are key elements of communicative competence.

In the study, students who regularly participated in games like improvisation, "frozen pictures", character switching, and dialogue transformation not only improved linguistically but also demonstrated increased motivation and enjoyment during English lessons.

A particularly notable outcome was the growth in students' confidence. This supports the ideas of Horwitz et al. [7], who emphasized that language anxiety can severely hinder performance, especially in oral tasks. Theatrical games helped reduce this anxiety by shifting the focus from correctness to creativity, allowing students to make mistakes without fear of judgment.

Furthermore, emotional engagement - often missing in traditional speaking exercises - became a central driver of active participation. Vygotsky's theory of play as a zone of proximal development

is relevant here: when students take on roles, they operate at a higher communicative level than in non-dramatic situations, enabling accelerated language growth.

The experimental group's progress in vocabulary usage and pronunciation accuracy aligns with studies by Schewe and Shaw [6], who demonstrated that drama encourages learners to internalize vocabulary more deeply through embodiment and context. Students don't just learn new words - they use them purposefully while "being" someone else in a scene, making the acquisition more meaningful.

Additionally, the emphasis on intonation, rhythm, and physical expression in theatrical games improves pronunciation and natural speech patterns, which were confirmed by both observational data and post-test results in our research.

Limitations

Despite the promising results, some limitations must be acknowledged:

1. The groups were not randomly selected, which may introduce bias.
2. The teacher was also the evaluator, possibly influencing assessment objectivity.
3. The duration of the intervention was relatively short (6 weeks), and longer exposure might yield even more pronounced results.

Future studies might consider involving external raters, longitudinal designs, or mixed-methods approaches to further investigate the long-term impact of drama in language education.

Conclusion

The present study confirms the pedagogical value of theatrical games in fostering the oral communicative competence of senior students learning English. The experimental group, which regularly participated in drama-based tasks such as role-plays, improvisations, and character-driven dialogues, demonstrated significantly higher gains in fluency, vocabulary range, pronunciation, and confidence compared to the control group.

Theatrical techniques not only provide a meaningful communicative context, but also help reduce speech anxiety, increase learners' motivation, and develop social and emotional engagement with language. These findings are supported by both quantitative data and observations, which consistently revealed deeper involvement and more natural speech production in the experimental group.

Despite the positive results, the practical implementation of theater games requires teacher training to strengthen their confidence in dramatic techniques and effective classroom management. Time constraints and curriculum requirements may require the selective introduction of short, focused theatrical activities instead of long dramatic sessions. In the future, digital tools such as interactive role-playing game applications or VR scenarios can be considered to increase accessibility and engagement. Combining theater games with other communicative methods, such as task-based learning or peer feedback, can enhance the effect for different types of students and educational settings.

Given the results, it is recommended that theatrical activities be systematically incorporated into the English language curriculum at the senior school level, especially when aiming to strengthen speaking skills. While the study had certain limitations - such as non-randomized groups and a limited time span - it lays important groundwork for further research involving larger samples, external assessment, and long-term observation of skill retention.

The integration of drama into the language classroom is not merely an auxiliary technique but a powerful pedagogical strategy capable of bridging the gap between language knowledge and real-world communication.

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